

12th International Conference on Web services & Semantic Technology (WeST 2020)

November 28 ~ 29, 2020, London, United Kingdom

<https://cndc2020.org/west/index.html>

Scope & Topics

12th International Conference on Web services & Semantic Technology (WeST 2020) will provide an excellent international forum for sharing knowledge and results in theory, methodology and applications of web & semantic technology. The growth of the World-Wide Web today is simply phenomenal. It continues to grow rapidly and new technologies, applications are being developed to support end users modern life. Semantic Technologies are designed to extend the capabilities of information on the Web and enterprise databases to be networked in meaningful ways. Semantic web is emerging as a core discipline in the field of Computer Science & Engineering from distributed computing, web engineering, databases, social networks, Multimedia, information systems, artificial intelligence, natural language processing, soft computing and human-computer interaction. The adoption of standards like XML, Resource Description Framework and Web Ontology Language serve as foundation technologies to advancing the adoption of semantic technologies.

The aim of the Conference is to provide a platform to the researchers and practitioners from both academia as well as industry to meet and share cutting-edge development in the field.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following:

- Aspect Oriented Programming
- Semantic Query & Search
- Semantic Advertising and Marketing
- Linked Data, Taxonomies
- Collaboration and Social Networks
- Semantic Web and Web 2.0/AJAX, Web 3.0
- Semantic Case Studies
- Ontologies (Creation , Merging, Linking and Reconciliation)
- Semantic Integration, Rules
- Data Integration and Mash ups
- Unstructured Information
- Developing Semantic Applications
- Semantics for Enterprise Information Management (EIM)
- Knowledge Engineering and Management
- Semantic SOA (Service Oriented Architectures)
- Database Technologies For the Semantic Web
- Semantic Web For E-Business, Governance and E-Learning
- Virtualization
- Semantic Brokering, Semantic Interoperability, Semantic Web Mining
- Semantic Web Services (Service Description, Discovery, Invocation, Composition)
- Semantic Web Trust, Privacy, Security and Intellectual Property Rights

- Information Discovery and Retrieval in Semantic Web
- Web Services Foundation, Architectures and Frameworks
- Web Languages & Web Service Applications
- Web Services-Driven Business Process Management
- Collaborative Systems Techniques
- Communication, Multimedia Applications Using Web Services
- Federated Identity Management Systems
- Interoperability and Standards
- Social and Legal Aspect of Internet Computing
- Internet and Web-based Applications and Services

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers through the conference [Submission System](#) by **July 26, 2020**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this conference. The proceedings of the conference will be published by [Computer Science Conference Proceedings](#) in [Computer Science & Information Technology \(CS & IT\)](#) series (Confirmed).

Selected papers from **WeST 2020**, after further revisions, will be published in the special issues of the following journals

- [International Journal of Web & Semantic Technology \(IJWesT\)](#)
- [International Journal on Web Service Computing \(IJWSC\)](#)
- [International Journal of Distributed and Parallel Systems \(IJDPS\)](#)
- [Information Technology in Industry \(ITII\)](#)^{New}-ESCI(WOS) Indexed

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : July 26, 2020**
- Authors Notification : September 11, 2020
- Registration & Camera-Ready Paper Due : September 19, 2020

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us : westconf@yahoo.com or west@cndc2020.org